

Effects of Treadmill Training with and without Mirror Therapy on Lower Limb Function, Dynamic Balance, and Gait in Chronic Stroke Patients

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Abstract:

Stroke, a brain attack, causes approximately 17 million new strokes annually, leading to motor deficits in up to 80% of patients, 30% experiencing long-term deficits in independent walking, and two-thirds experiencing functional limitations in lower limbs. The objective of this research is to determine the effect of treadmill training with and without mirror therapy on lower limb function, dynamic balance, and gait in chronic stroke patients. This research involved 24 chronic stroke patients divided into two groups: Group A received lower-limb treadmill training with mirror treatment, and Group B received treadmill training without mirror treatment. Both

groups received traditional physiotherapy methods. The study found that MAS was non-parametric, while other measures were parametric. The trial lasted eight weeks, using six-minute walk testing, the modified Ashworth scale, and Fugl-Meyer assessment (lower extremity). The study found that the "mirror therapy" group had better results than the "control group" group, with P values of 0.023 and 0.00, respectively, for the outcome measures "MAS post-intervention" and "6MWT post-intervention." The "Mirror Therapy" group also improved more than the "Control Group" group in the outcome measure "FMA-LE Post-Intervention." This study concluded that there was a significant association between treadmill training and mirror therapy and lower limb functioning, dynamic balance, and gait in chronic stroke patients.

Keywords: *Gait, motor skills disorder, postural balance, stroke, treadmill tests, walking speed.*

Introduction

A stroke is a neurological disorder brought on by a disruption in blood flow to the brain, which causes the brain's cells to die (Kim et al., 2019). Up to 80% of stroke patients experience motor deficits, which are frequently characterized by

paresis and spasticity of the paretic limb (Caplan, 2016; Phipps & Cronin, 2020).

In stroke patients, hemiparesis, a common impairment, can lessen joint mobility and muscle contraction force. This motor impairment can also make a person's body unbalanced, reduce their gait endurance and balance, and make them

fearful of falling while they exercise(Govindarajan et al., 2020). In order to manage the permanent problems that result from a stroke, individuals need long-term care(Goh et al., 2016).

Research shows 32% of stroke survivors struggle with daily activities, 62% needing assistance post-therapy, with walking being a key skill lost by 80% of stroke patients. (Schinkel-Ivy et al., 2016). Impaired balance is regarded as a precursor to falling, reducing motion, and lowering the quality of life. As a result, the imbalance loop continues, delaying the recovery and rehabilitation strategy(Liu et al., 2019).

Despite the fact that most stroke patients can walk six months after their stroke, 40% of them still require assistance when walking, and 60% have problems accessing their local communities(De Amorim et al., 2017; Ojaghihaghghi et al., 2017). Recovery of walking ability is an important objective in the treatment of stroke to allow patients to regain independence and improve their quality of life. During the chronic phase of a stroke, motor recovery stabilizes, and patients must adjust to environmental changes(De Amorim et al., 2017; Divani et al., 2020).

In specifically, lower limb motor performance paralysis negatively impacts balance and walking abilities, increasing the risk of falling. Exercise training, including pre-walking functional activities and weight transition, is a crucial part of post-stroke physical therapy, focusing on active, repetitive movements affecting the paralyzed limbs(Ashford et al., 2015).

Therapeutic therapies aim to help stroke survivors regain walking capacity, restoring balance and postural symmetry through walking exercises, which are a fundamental component of therapy (Dorsch et al., 2016). Previous studies have suggested various methods to improve patients' gait, including strengthening weak dorsiflexion, body weight support training, rhythmic auditory stimulation, virtual reality, robot-assisted gait, and circuit class treatment. (Mao et al., 2015).

Focused workout time can enhance motor function recovery through lower-limb weight training, circuit-group exercise, underwater treadmill exercise, treadmill walking, and functional electric stimulation therapy(Mentiplay et al., 2015).

Cueing significantly affects the gait pattern and balance in post-stroke rehabilitation protocols. Cues, which can be verbal, haptic, or auditory, improve a chronic stroke survivor's cadence, gait speed, and double support(Arya et al., 2017).

Shepherd and Carr developed task-oriented gait rehab training in the 1980s to improve walking speed and mobility in stroke patients, controlling their characteristics for effective intervention tactics. (Stanton et al., 2017).

Mirror therapy training is an effective task-oriented therapy for stroke patients, stimulating motor cortex activity and visual feedback, and remodeling the cerebral cortex(Gibbons et al., 2016). Studies compare paretic sensory motor training therapy with visual stimulus, highlighting balance issues in chronic stroke patients with somatosensory loss and impaired muscle tone (Lee et al., 2015). Stroke therapy aims to restore functional independence, requiring adequate balance for post-stroke survivors, regardless of demographics or recovery time (Lee et al., 2019).

Mirror therapy and treadmill training can enhance motor cortex excitability and reduce motor impairments by providing visual feedback and weight bearing, respectively.

Objective

To determine the effects of treadmill training with and without mirror therapy on lower limb function, dynamic balance, and gait in chronic stroke patients.

Material and Methods

This randomized controlled trial, conducted at the Physiotherapy Department of a Pakistani hospital over 10 months, compared the effects of mirror therapy combined with treadmill training versus treadmill training alone for

chronic stroke patients. 26 participants (12 per group) were conveniently selected based on specific criteria: age 35-65, stroke duration 6 months-4 years, no walking aids needed, and normal cognition. Those with movement disorders, vision problems, epilepsy, surgery/fractures, or aphasia were excluded. Assessments (Modified Ashworth Scale, 6-Minute Walk Test, Fugl-Meyer Assessment) were performed at baseline and after 10 months to measure muscle tone, endurance, and sensorimotor function, respectively.

Study Groups

Group A: Interventional Group (Mirror therapy with treadmill training along with conventional physiotherapy treatment).

Group B: Control Group (Treadmill training without mirror therapy along with conventional physiotherapy treatment)

Data Collection Tools

Data was collected using the following instruments:

Modified Ashworth scale

Six points make up the Modified Ashworth Scale. Low scores indicate normal muscular tone, whereas high levels indicate spasticity. Scores range from 0 to 4. Intra-rater consistency (73.3%)(Yoo et al., 2022).

6 – Minute Walk Test

It is a moderate-intensity exercise test that evaluates one's endurance and aerobic capacity. The outcome by which to evaluate changes in physical performance is the distance traveled during a period of 6 minutes. Reproducibility of tests (ICC = 0.99)(Johnson et al., 2019).

Fugl – Meyer Assessment for Lower Extremity

A gauge to measure sensorimotor dysfunction in stroke survivors is the Fugl-Meyer Assessment (FMA) scale. The scale measures reflex activity and voluntary movements performed both within and outside of synergies, synchronization, and the capacity to carry out solitary motions. Inter-rater consistency (ICC 0.88–0.95)(Selves et al., 2020).

Data Collection Procedure

After being screened for eligibility and providing informed consent, stroke patients were randomly assigned to either the intervention group (treadmill training with mirror therapy) or the control group (treadmill training without mirror therapy). Both groups received traditional physiotherapy and underwent pre-intervention assessments (Modified Ashworth Scale, 6-Minute Walk Test, Fugl-Meyer Assessment). For 8 weeks, participants in both groups walked on a treadmill for 30 minutes, 3 days a week. Therapists provided verbal commands and adjusted speed, while patients used handrails as needed. During treadmill training, the intervention group observed a reflection of their non-paretic leg in a mirror positioned to optimize movement visualization and were instructed to focus on their reflected leg while walking.

Following the intervention, both groups were re-evaluated, and data was analyzed using SPSS software.

Data Analysis

Data analysis was performed using SPSS v27, with statistical significance set at $p=0.05$. Descriptive statistics (frequency tables, pie charts, histograms) were used to characterize the data. To assess within-group changes, paired sample t-tests were employed to compare pre- and post-treatment scores on both subjective and objective measures. For between-group comparisons, independent sample t-tests were used to evaluate differences between intervention and control groups.

Results

The study analyzed the gender distribution in a mirror therapy group and a control group. The "Mirror Therapy" group had a higher proportion of males (66.7%) and females (33.3%), while the "Control Group" had a lower proportion of males (50%). The affected limb distribution was different in both groups. The mean age of the "Mirror Therapy" group was 51.49, while the mean age of the "Control Group" group was

55.37. The onset of the condition was also not statistically significant. The MAS was non-parametric, while the other measures were parametric. The mean rank for the "Mirror Therapy" group was 13.00, with a sum of ranks of 156.00. The Mann-Whitney U test score was 66.00, and the Wilcoxon W test score was 144.00. The Z score was -0.401, and the p-value was 0.688, indicating no statistically significant difference between the two groups.

The study involved 12 participants in both "Mirror Therapy" and "Control Group" groups. The results showed a statistically significant difference between the two groups for the "MAS Post-Intervention" and "6MWT Baseline" outcomes. The Mirror Therapy group had better results than the Control group. The mean rank for the "Mirror Therapy" group was 9.67, with a sum of ranks of 116.00. The mean difference between the two groups was -3.50, with a P value of 0.54. The mean difference between the two groups was 24.67, with a P value of 0.00. The mean difference between the two groups for the "FMA-LE Baseline" outcome was 32.42, with a P value of 0.40. The mean difference between

the two groups for the "MAS Post-Intervention - MAS Baseline" outcome was 6.50, with a P value of 0.002, suggesting a statistically significant difference between the two groups.

The study found a significant difference in performance between the "Mirror Therapy" and "Control Group" groups in the "6MWT Baseline" and "FMA-LE Baseline" outcomes. The mean difference between the two groups was -48.50, with a t-value of -27.22 and a P value of 0.00. The mean difference was not provided for the "6MWT post-Intervention" outcome measure. The mean difference for the "FMA-LE Baseline" outcome measure was 32.42, with a t-value of 3.65 and a P value of 0.00. The mean difference for the "FMA-LE Post-Intervention" outcome measure was 44.58, with a t-value of 4.10. The results suggest that the "Mirror Therapy" group performed worse than the "Control Group" group at baseline for both 6MWT and FMA-LE. However, the post-intervention outcomes were not provided, making it unclear how these groups performed after the intervention.

Table 1. Gender

Group		Frequency	Percent
Mirror Therapy	Male	8	66.7
	Female	4	33.3
	Total	12	100.0
Control Group	Male	6	50.0
	Female	6	50.0
	Total	12	100.0

The results showed that in the "Mirror Therapy" group, there were 8 males (66.7%) and 4 females (33.3%) for a total of 12 participants (100%). In the "Control Group," there were 6 males (50%)

and 6 females (50%) for a total of 12 participants (100%). This suggests that the gender distribution is similar in both groups.

Table 2. Side Involved

Group		Frequency	Percent
Mirror Therapy	Right	4	33.3
	Left	8	66.7
	Total	12	100.0
Control Group	Right	2	16.7
	Left	10	83.3
	Total	12	100.0

The results showed that in the "Mirror Therapy" group, there were 4 participants (33.3%) with right-side affected limbs and 8 participants (66.7%) with left-side affected limbs, for a total of 12 participants (100%). In the "Control Group," there were 2 participants (16.7%) with

right-side affected limb and 10 participants (83.3%) with left-side affected limb, for a total of 12 participants (100%). This suggests that the affected limb distribution is different in both groups.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	P Value
Age	Mirror Therapy	51.49	6.15	0.121
	Control Group	55.37	5.62	
Onset	Mirror Therapy	20.00	8.01	0.563
	Control Group	22.00	8.64	

The results showed that the mean age of participants in the "Mirror Therapy" group is 51.49, with a standard deviation of 6.15. The mean age of participants in the "Control Group" is 55.37, with a standard deviation of 5.62. The P value for the difference in mean age between the two groups is 0.121, which suggests that the difference in age between the two groups is not statistically significant.

The results also showed that the mean onset of the condition for participants in the "Mirror Therapy" group is 20.00, with a standard deviation of 8.01. The mean onset of the condition for participants in the "Control Group" is 22.00, with a standard deviation of 8.64. The P value for the difference in mean onset between the two groups is 0.563, which suggests that the difference in onset between the two groups is not statistically significant.

The results regarding the onset histogram in mirror therapy showed a mean to be 20.00 and a standard deviation to be 8.01.

Figure 2. Age Control Group

The results regarding the age histogram in the control group showed a mean to be 55.37 and a standard deviation to be 5.62.

Figure 1. Onset Mirror Therapy

Figure 3. Onset Control Group

The results regarding the onset histogram in the control group showed a mean to be 22.00 and a standard deviation to be 8.64.

Table 4 Tests of Normality

Outcome Measures	Kolmogorov-Smirnova			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
MAS Baseline	.358	24	.000	.637	24	.000
MAS Post-Intervention	.318	24	.000	.778	24	.000
6MWT Baseline	.127	24	.200*	.906	24	.069
6MWT post-Intervention	.072	24	.200*	.987	24	.987
FMA-LE Baseline	.161	24	.110	.920	24	.059
FMA-LE Post-Intervention	.145	24	.200*	.960	24	.435

The tests of normality showed MAS to be non-parametric, p-value < 0.05, while the rest of the

measures, 6MWT and FMA-LE, to be parametric, p-value > 0.05.

Table 5. Comparison of Mirror and Control Therapy by Mann Whitney U Test

Outcome Measures	Group	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mann-Whitney U	Wilcoxon W	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
MAS Baseline	Mirror Therapy	13.00	156.00	66.00	144.00	- 0.401	0.688
	Control Group	12.00	144.00				
MAS Post-Intervention	Mirror Therapy	9.67	116.00	38.00	116.00	- 2.277	0.023
	Control Group	15.33	184.00				

The study analyzed the results of two outcomes measures, "MAS Baseline" and "MAS Post-Intervention". The "Mirror Therapy" group had a mean rank of 13.00, with a sum of ranks of 156.00. The Mann-Whitney U test score was 66.00, and the Wilcoxon W test score was 144.00. The Z score was -0.401, and the p-value was 0.688. However, there was no statistically

significant difference between the two groups for the "MAS Post-Intervention" measure. The mean rank for the "Mirror Therapy" group was 9.67, with a sum of ranks of 116.00. The Mann-Whitney U test score was 38.00, and the Wilcoxon W test score was 116.00. The Z score was -2.277, and the p-value was 0.023.

Table 6. Comparison of Means by Independent Samples t Test

Outcome Measures	Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference	P Value
6MWT Baseline	Mirror Therapy	309.25	12.00	-3.50	0.54
	Control Group	312.75	15.00		
6MWT post-Intervention	Mirror Therapy	357.75	14.48	24.67	0.00
	Control Group	333.08	13.56		
FMA-LE Baseline	Mirror Therapy	32.42	3.65	-1.17	0.40
	Control Group	33.58	2.94		
FMA-LE Post-Intervention	Mirror Therapy	44.58	4.10	3.91	0.023
	Control Group	40.66	3.72		

The results show that for the outcome measure "6MWT Baseline," there were participants in

both the "Mirror Therapy" and "Control Group" groups. The P value is 0.54. This

suggests that there is no statistically significant difference between the "Mirror Therapy" and "Control Group" groups for this outcome measure. For the outcome measure "6MWT post- Intervention," The P value is 0.00. This suggests that there is a statistically significant difference between the "Mirror Therapy" and "Control Group" groups for this outcome measure. The Mirror therapy group has better results than the Control group.

For the outcome measure "FMA-LE Baseline," the P value is 0.40. This suggests that there is no statistically significant difference between the "Mirror Therapy" and "Control Group" groups for this outcome measure. For the outcome measure "FMA-LE Post-Intervention," the P value is 0.023. This suggests that there is a statistically significant difference between the "Mirror Therapy" and "Control Group" groups for this outcome measure. The Mirror therapy group has better results than the Control group.

Table 7. Modified Ashworth Scale Within Mirror Therapy and Control Therapy

Group			N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Z	P Value
Mirror Therapy	MAS Post- Intervention - MAS Baseline	Negative Ranks	12a	6.50	78.00	-3.140	0.002
		Positive Ranks	0b	.00	.00		
		Ties	0c				
		Total	12				
Control Group	MAS Post- Intervention - MAS Baseline	Negative Ranks	12a	6.50	78.00	-3.35	0.001
		Positive Ranks	0b	.00	.00		
		Ties	0c				
		Total	12				
a. MAS Post-Intervention < MAS Baseline							
b. MAS Post-Intervention > MAS Baseline							
c. MAS Post-Intervention = MAS Baseline							

The results show that for the "MAS Post-Intervention - MAS Baseline" outcome measure. The mean rank for the "Mirror Therapy" group is 6.50, with a sum of ranks of 78.00, and the Z score is -3.140. The P value is 0.002, which suggests that there is a statistically significant difference between the "Mirror Therapy" group and the "Control Group" group for this

outcome measure. In both groups, there were no positive ranks or ties, and all participants had negative ranks. This suggests that participants in both groups improved on the MAS scale but more so in the Mirror therapy group. This suggests that the "Mirror Therapy" group had a greater improvement in the MAS scale when compared to the "Control Group."

Table 8. Paired Sample t-test

Group		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	t	P Value
Mirror Therapy	6MWT Baseline	309.25	12.00	-48.50	-27.22	0.00
	6MWT post-Intervention	357.75	14.48			
	FMA-LE Baseline	32.42	3.65	-12.17	-37.81	0.00
	FMA-LE Post-Intervention	44.58	4.10			
Control Group	6MWT Baseline	312.75	15.00	-20.33	-7.97	0.00
	6MWT post-Intervention	333.08	13.56			
	FMA-LE Baseline	33.58	2.94	-7.08	-12.42	0.00
	FMA-LE Post-Intervention	40.67	3.73			

The results show that for the "6MWT Baseline" outcome measure, the P value is 0.00. This

suggests that there is a statistically significant difference between the "Mirror Therapy" group

and the "Control Group" group for this outcome measure, with the "Mirror Therapy" group performing worse than the "Control Group" group at baseline, for the "6MWT post-Intervention" outcome measure. The mean difference is not provided, and the P value is not provided.

For the "FMA-LE Baseline" outcome measure, the t-value is -37.81, and the P-value is 0.00. This suggests that there is a statistically significant difference between the "Mirror Therapy" group and the "Control Group" group for this outcome measure, with the "Mirror Therapy" group performing worse than the "Control Group" group at baseline. For the "FMA-LE Post-Intervention" outcome measure, the mean for the "Mirror Therapy" group is 44.58, with a standard deviation of 4.10. The mean difference is not provided, and the P value is not provided. The results suggest that the "Mirror Therapy" group performed worse than the "Control Group" group at baseline for 6MWT and FMA-LE.

Discussion

The study showed that the "Mirror Therapy" group had better results than the "Control Group" group with P values of 0.023 and 0.00, respectively, for the outcome measures "MAS Post- Intervention" and "6MWT post-Intervention". The "Mirror Therapy" group also improved more than the "Control Group" group in the outcome measure "MAS Post-Intervention - MAS Baseline," with a P value of 0.002. But for the outcome measure "6MWT Baseline," the "Mirrortherapy" group performed worse than the "Control Group" group with a P value of 0.00.

According to the study by Broderick P et al. in 2019, the author used mirror therapy contrasted with placebo mirror therapy. But in his study, they had concluded that there was no significant improvement noted in 10MWT, 6MWT, and in FMA-LE but on the same point author found significant improvement in the group for the MAS, specifically in ankle dorsiflexors muscular tone but in the current study reported

statistically significant improvement in all outcome measures (Broderick, Horgan, Blake, Ehrensberger, et al., 2019).

The study performed by Kim et al. in 2015 found that when mirror therapeutic training and virtual therapeutic training were given to the lower extremities of individuals with subacute stroke 5 times a week for 4 weeks, sole support, step, and stride length were dramatically improved in the experimental class. When comparing pre- and post-treatment standing and walking tests, they found that mirror therapy drastically enhanced the lower limb function of stroke victims. As Kim et al. reported statistically significant improvement in the mirror therapy group as per our current study, currently author deduced that the mirror therapy group had shown statistically significant improvement as per p-value is 0.00 and 0.023 in lower limb functioning and dynamic balance in stroke patients along with these outcomes measure MAS score was also improved significantly as per correlating with previous evidence.

A previous study by Kim et al. in 2017 concluded that alongside conventional physiotherapy activities, low extremity mobility and muscle strengthening exercises employing mirrors had a favorable impact on lower extremity functions in stroke victims and the restoration of the paralyzed side, resulting in a noticeable change in balance and walking skills ($p < 0.05$) (Kim et al., 2018). All of this evidence, along with our current study, suggests that physiotherapy was showing improvement in outcome measure as per calculating Baselines, but conventional physiotherapy along with mirror therapy showed positive ties to the literature that this therapy had a positive impact on the functionality of patients.

The fact that both experimental groups' walking abilities significantly increased shows that the intervention strategy improved participants' static and dynamic balance as well as their capacity to walk (symmetric movement) (Yoo et al., 2022).

These findings suggest that walking requires symmetrical motion. Because the control group

was not given the visual input, they were unable to learn the symmetrical motion.

The research shows that symmetrical visual feedback via a mirror improves gait parameters, balance, step length, stride length, and step breadth, without affecting rhythm or walking speed (Sütbeyaz et al., 2007). Studies show that chronic stroke patients receiving treadmill training, mirror therapy, and conventional physiotherapy programs significantly improve lower limb functioning, spasticity, gait patterns, and dynamic balance.

Conclusion

This study concluded that there was a strong effect of treadmill training with mirror therapy on lower limb functioning, dynamic balance, and gait in chronic stroke patients. The group with mirror therapy along with treadmill training showed improvement in lower limb functioning, dynamic balance, and gait of stroke patients compared to the group without mirror therapy along with treadmill training.

Limitations Of Study

First, the relatively low dose of medication (pharmacotherapy) may have had an impact on the efficacy of the treatment.

Second, there was only one outcome assessment made at each time point. More evaluations could increase the accuracy of participant grading.

Third, participants had to look down while walking in order to look at the mirror treatment equipment. The participant's performance in the applicable outcome measures may have been affected by this approach to gait, which detracts from the typical stance while walking.

Recommendations

This study recommends assessing the long-term effect of treadmill training with or without mirror therapy on lower limb function, dynamic stability, and gait in chronic stroke patients with a relatively large sample size.

To completely assess the functional benefit, follow-up mirror treatment studies should compare the therapeutic results according to the exercise done during the stroke onset period.

Lower limb mirror treatment should include changes in intervention dosage in order to determine the proper dose levels of treatment so that patients may get maximum benefit.

Availability of Data and Materials

Data is available on reasonable demand.

Competing Interests

There are no competing interests.

Funding

This was a self-funded study.

Authors' contributions

1, 2 and 3 wrote the literature review.

1 wrote the manuscript with support from 2.

1 and 3 carried out the data collection and analysis.

2 helped supervise the project.

1, 2 and 3 conceived the original idea.

2 supervised the project.

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List of Abbreviations

Serial	Abbreviation	Description
1.	FMA-LE	Fugl-Meyer assessment-Lower Extremity
2.	MWT	Minute Walk Test
3.	VR	Virtual Reality
4.	MT	Mirror Therapy
5.	BBS	Berg Balance Scale
6.	TUG	Timed up & go
7.	FRT	Functional Reach Test
8.	LOS	Limit of Stability
9.	MMSE	Mini-Mental State Examination
10.	SPSS	Statistical Package of Social Science
11.	ICC	Intra class coefficient
12.	LE	Lower Extremity